

LINEAR GEOMETRY: PROSCALARS IN PROJECTIVE LINERS

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ABSTRACT. Linear Geometry describes geometric properties that depend on the notion of a line. In this survey we study projective spaces and show that every projective space carries a canonical field of proscalars. Using this algebraic structure we provide an isomorphic classification of Desarguesian and Pappian projective (more generally, proaffine) spaces.

INTRODUCTION

This paper is the sixth survey in the series of surveys that describe the contents of the monograph “Linear Geometry and Algebra” [1] of the author. The first survey [2] concentrated at properties of liners that depend on flat hulls (flats, ranks, regularity, parallelity); the second survey [3] discussed completions and projectivizations of liners; the third survey [4] discussed Desarguesian, Pappian and Thalesian liners; the fourth survey [5] concentrated at special automorphisms of liners (dilations, translations, and hypershears), and some special bijections between lines in affine and projective liners (line projections, line translations, line affinities, line perspectivities, line projectivities); the fifth survey [6] discussed vector algebra in affine spaces. In this survey we show that projective spaces possess a canonical field of proscalars and will apply this algebraic structure to isomorphic classification of Desarguesian and Pappian projective and proaffine spaces. The material of this survey covers Chapters 18, 23, 24 of the book [1].

1. PRELIMINARIES

In this section we recall some basic notions of Linear Geometry, needed for understanding the main results of this survey.

A *liner* is a set X of *points*, endowed with a family \mathcal{L} of subsets of X called *lines* such that the following two axioms are satisfied:

- any two distinct points belong to a unique line;
- any line contains at least two distinct points.

For two distinct points x, y of a liner X , we denote by \overline{xy} the unique line containing those points. If $x = y$, then we put $\overline{xy} := \{x\} = \{y\}$.

A liner X is *κ -long* for a cardinal κ if every line L in X has cardinality $|L| \geq \kappa$. A liner X is called *Steiner* if every line L in X has cardinality $|L| = 3$.

A bijective map $F : X \rightarrow Y$ between two liners (X, \mathcal{L}_X) and (Y, \mathcal{L}_Y) is called a *liner isomorphism* if $\mathcal{L}_Y = \{F[L] : L \in \mathcal{L}_X\}$. An *automorphism* of a liner X is any isomorphism $F : X \rightarrow X$. The set $\text{Aut}(X)$ of all automorphisms of a liner X is a group with respect to the operation of composition of automorphisms.

Each subset $A \subseteq X$ of a liner (X, \mathcal{L}) carries the line structure

$$\mathcal{L}_A := \{L \cap A : L \in \mathcal{L} \wedge |L \cap A| \geq 2\}$$

turning A into a liner, called a *subliner* of the liner (X, \mathcal{L}) .

A subset $A \subseteq X$ of a liner X is called *flat* if $\overline{xy} \subseteq A$ for any points $x, y \in A$. For a subset $A \subseteq X$ its *flat hull* \overline{A} is the smallest flat set in X that contains the set A . The *rank* $\|A\|$ of a set $A \subseteq X$ is the smallest cardinality of a subset $B \subseteq X$ such that $A \subseteq \overline{B}$. Flat subsets of rank 3 in a liner are called *planes*. A proper flat H in a liner X is called a *hyperplane* if every flat F in X with $H \subseteq F \subseteq X$ is equal to H or X . The *dimension* $\dim(X)$ of a liner X is the unique cardinal κ such that $1 + \kappa = \|X\|$.

A subset A of a liner X is called

- *independent* if $x \notin \overline{A \setminus \{x\}}$ for all $x \in A$;
- *maximal independent* if $A = M$ for any independent set $M \subseteq X$ that contains A .

A liner X is called

- *strongly regular* if for every nonempty flat $A \subseteq X$ and point $b \in X \setminus A$, we have $\overline{A \cup \{b\}} = \bigcup_{a \in A} \overline{a b}$;
- *regular* if for every flat $A \subseteq X$ and points $o \in A$, $b \in X \setminus A$ we have $\overline{A \cup \{b\}} = \bigcup_{a \in A} \bigcup_{y \in \overline{o b}} \overline{a y}$.

A liner X is *ranked* (resp. *κ -ranked* for a cardinal number κ) if for any distinct flats $A \subset B$ of finite rank (with $\|B\| \leq \kappa$) we have $\|A\| < \|B\|$. By [1, 3.1.6], every regular liner is ranked.

Let κ and λ be cardinals. A liner X is defined to be *κ -balanced* with $|X|_\kappa = \lambda$ if every flat $F \subseteq X$ of rank $\|F\| = \kappa$ has cardinality $|F| = \lambda$. A liner X is called *κ -balanced* if it is κ -balanced with $|X|_\kappa = \lambda$ for some cardinal λ . A liner X is *balanced* if it is κ -balanced for all cardinals κ .

A liner X is defined to be

- *projective* if $\forall o, x, y \in X \ \forall p \in \overline{x y} \ \forall v \in \overline{o y} \setminus \{p\} \ (v \overline{p} \cap \overline{o x} \neq \emptyset)$;
- *proaffine* if $\forall o, x, y \in X \ \forall p \in \overline{x y} \setminus \overline{o x} \ \exists u \in \overline{o y} \ \forall v \in \overline{o y} \setminus \{u\} \ (v \overline{p} \cap \overline{o x} \neq \emptyset)$;
- *affine* if $\forall o, x, y \in X \ \forall p \in \overline{x y} \setminus \overline{o x} \ \exists u \in \overline{o y} \ \forall v \in \overline{o y} \ (u = v \Leftrightarrow v \overline{p} \cap \overline{o x} = \emptyset)$.

A liner is proaffine if it is projective or affine. By [1, 3.3.17], every affine liner X is 2-balanced. The cardinal $|X|_2$ (equal to the cardinality of any line in X) is called the *order* of the affine liner X . By [1, 3.3.24], every 3-long projective liner X is 2-balanced. The cardinal $|X|_2 - 1$ is called the *order* of the projective liner X . By [1, 3.4.1], a liner is projective if and only if it is strongly regular.

A liner X is called

- *Desarguesian* if for any plane $\Pi \subseteq X$, distinct lines A, B, C in Π and any distinct points $o \in A \cap B \cap C$, $a, a' \in A$, $b, b' \in B$, $c, c' \in C$, the set $T := (\overline{a b} \cap \overline{a' b'}) \cup (\overline{b c} \cap \overline{b' c'}) \cup (\overline{a c} \cap \overline{a' c'})$ has rank $\|T\| \in \{0, 2\}$;
- *Moufang* if for any distinct lines A, B, C in X and any distinct points $o \in A \cap B \cap C$, $a, a' \in A$, $b, b' \in B$, $c, c' \in C$ with $b' \in \overline{a c}$, the set $T := (\overline{a b} \cap \overline{a' b'}) \cup (\overline{b c} \cap \overline{b' c'}) \cup (\overline{a c} \cap \overline{a' c'})$ has rank $\|T\| \in \{0, 2\}$;
- *Pappian* if for any concurrent lines L, L' in X and any distinct points $a, b, c \in L \setminus L'$, $a', b', c' \in L' \setminus L$, the set $T := (\overline{a b'} \cap \overline{a' b}) \cup (\overline{b c'} \cap \overline{b' c}) \cup (\overline{a c'} \cap \overline{a' c})$ has rank $\|T\| \in \{0, 2\}$;
- *Thalesian* if for every plane $\Pi \subseteq X$, any disjoint lines $A, B, C \subseteq \Pi$ and points $a, a' \in A$, $b, b' \in B$, $c, c' \in C$, the equalities $\overline{a b} \cap \overline{a' b'} = \emptyset = \overline{b c} \cap \overline{b' c'}$ implies $\overline{a c} \cap \overline{a' c'} = \emptyset$.

By [1, 10.4.5], every 3-long proaffine regular liner X of rank $\|X\| \neq 3$ is Desarguesian; by Hesse's Theorem [1, 20.5.1], every Pappian proaffine regular liner is Desarguesian; it is easy to see that every Desarguesian liner is Moufang; by [1, 11.1.5], every Desarguesian proaffine regular liner is Thalesian. Therefore, for every proaffine regular liner we have the implications: Pappian \Rightarrow Desarguesian \Rightarrow Thalesian. By [1, 11.2.1], a projective liner X is Moufang if and only if it is everywhere Thalesian in the sense that for every hyperplane $H \subset X$, the affine subliner $X \setminus H$ is Thalesian.

A liner X is called

- an *affine space* if X is 3-long, affine, regular and has rank $\|X\| \geq 3$;
- a *projective space* if X is 3-long, projective, and has rank $\|X\| \geq 3$.

A *projective completion* of a liner X is any 3-long projective liner Y containing X as a subliner such that $\overline{Y \setminus X} \neq Y$. The set $Y \setminus X$ is called the *horizon* of X in Y . More information on projective completions of liners can be found in Chapter 8 of the monograph [1].

An important example of a projective completion is the spread completion of a completely regular liner. Spread completions of liners are introduced and studied in Chapter 7 of the monograph [1]. Here we briefly recall that the definition of the spread completion of a 3-ranked liner.

Let X be a liner and \mathcal{L} be the family of all lines in X . A subfamily $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ is called a *spread of lines* in X if every point $x \in X$ belongs to a unique line $L \in \mathcal{S}$. A line $L \in \mathcal{L}$ is called *spreading* if the family $L_{\parallel} := \{\Lambda \in \mathcal{L} : \Lambda \parallel L\}$ is a spread of lines in X such that $L_{\parallel} = \Lambda_{\parallel}$ for every line $\Lambda \in L_{\parallel}$. In this case, the spread of parallel lines L_{\parallel} is called a *direction* in the liner X . Let \mathcal{S} be the family of all spreading lines in X . The family $\partial X := \{L_{\parallel} : L \in \mathcal{S}\}$ is called the *boundary* of the liner X . So, the boundary of X consists of all directions in X . For a plane $\Pi \subseteq X$, let $\partial\Pi = \{L_{\parallel} : L \in \mathcal{S} \wedge L \subseteq \Pi\}$ be the *boundary* of the plane Π in X . Let \mathcal{P} be the family of planes Π in X such that $|\partial\Pi| \geq 2$.

If the liner X is 3-ranked¹, then the set $\overline{X} = X \cup \partial X$ endowed with the family of lines

$$\overline{\mathcal{L}} := \{L \cup \{L_{\parallel}\} : L \in \mathcal{S}\} \cup \{\partial\Pi : \Pi \in \mathcal{P}\}$$

is a liner, called the *spread completion* of the liner X . A liner X is called *completely regular* if X is 3-ranked and its spread completion \overline{X} is strongly regular (= projective).

By Corollary 7.6.10 and Theorems 7.6.2 in [1], for every liner we have the implications:

$$\text{affine regular} \Rightarrow \text{strongly regular} \Rightarrow \text{completely regular} \Rightarrow \text{regular}.$$

By [1, 8.3.19], a completely regular liner X is affine if and only if its horizon $\overline{X} \setminus X$ is a hyperplane in \overline{X} . Conversely, for every hyperplane H in a projective liner Y , the subliner $Y \setminus H$ is affine and regular, by [1, 8.3.13].

For two flats A, B in a liner X , we say that A is *subparallel* to B and write $A \parallel B$ if $A \subseteq \overline{B \cup \{a\}}$ for all $a \in A$. We say that flats $A, B \subseteq X$ are *parallel* and write $A \parallel B$ if $A \parallel B$ and $B \parallel A$.

A bijection $F : L \rightarrow L'$ between two lines L, L' in a liner X is called a *line bijection* in X .

A line bijection $F : L \rightarrow L'$ in a liner X is called

- a *line projection* if there exists a line Λ in X such that $F = \{(x, y) \in L \times L' : \overline{xy} \parallel \Lambda\}$;
- a *line affinity* if F can be written as the composition of finitely many line projections;
- a *line perspectivity* if there exists a point $o \in X \setminus (L \cup L')$ such that $F = \{(x, y) \in L \times L' : \overline{ox} = \overline{oy}\}$;
- a *line projectivity* if F can be written as the composition of finitely many line perspectivities.

We think of functions as functional relations. For a relation F let $\text{dom}[F] := \{x : \exists y (x, y) \in F\}$ and $\text{rng}[F] := \{y : \exists x (x, y) \in F\}$ be the domain and range of F .

Lemma 1.1 ([1, 23.6.1]). *Let X be a projective completion of an affine space A . For every line projection P in A , the set $\overline{P} := P \cup ((\overline{\text{dom}[P]} \setminus A) \times (\overline{\text{rng}[P]} \setminus A))$ is a line perspectivity in X extending the line projection P .*

Lemma 1.2 ([1, 23.6.2]). *Let X be a projective completion of an affine space A . For every line affinity P in A , the set $\overline{P} := P \cup ((\overline{\text{dom}[P]} \setminus A) \times (\overline{\text{rng}[P]} \setminus A))$ is a line projectivity in X extending the line affinity P .*

Line affinities in affine space and line projectivities in projective spaces can be used to define interesting algebraic structures canonically related to affine or projective spaces. For an affine space such a canonical algebraic structure is the scalar corps of the affine space. Scalars in an affine space are equivalence classes of line triples under the relation of affine equivalence. Here we briefly recall the construction of the scalar corps of an affine space. The full details can be found in Chapter 16 of the book [1].

A triple $xyz \in X^3$ in a liner X is called a *line triple* if $x \neq z$ and $y \in \overline{xz}$. The set of all line triples in a liner X is denoted by \overline{X} . Given two line triples abc and xyz in an affine space X we write $abc \bowtie xyz$ say that abc and xyz are *affinely equivalent* if there exists a line affinity $A : \overline{ac} \rightarrow \overline{xz}$ in X such that $Aabc = xyz$. A line triple $ove \in X^3$ is called *Desarguesian* if for every line affinity A in X with $Aoe = oe$, we have $A(v) = v$. By [1, 16.2.5], an affine space X is Desarguesian if and only if every line triple in X is Desarguesian.

¹A liner X is 3-ranked, if any two planes $A \subseteq B$ in X are equal.

For a line triple $ove \in \ddot{X}$, its equivalence class $\overrightarrow{ove} := \{xyz \in \ddot{X} : xyz \bowtie ove\}$ is called the *portion* determined by the line triple ove . The portion \overrightarrow{ove} is called a *scalar* if the line triple ove is Desarguesian. By \mathbb{R}_X we denote the set of all scalars in an affine space X . The set \mathbb{R}_X contains two important scalars:

$$0 := \{ove \in X^3 : v = o \neq e\} \quad \text{and} \quad 1 := \{ove \in X^3 : v = e \neq o\}.$$

By [1, 16.6.3], the set $\mathbb{R}_X^* := \mathbb{R}_X \setminus \{0\}$ of nonzero scalars is a group with respect to the multiplication operation $\cdot : \mathbb{R}_X^* \times \mathbb{R}_X^* \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_X^*$, $\cdot : \overrightarrow{aab} \cdot \overrightarrow{obe} := \overrightarrow{aa\dot{e}}$. For every scalar $\overrightarrow{ove} \in \mathbb{R}_X^*$ its inverse $(\overrightarrow{ove})^{-1}$ in the group (\mathbb{R}_X^*, \cdot) coincides with the scalar \overrightarrow{oev} . The multiplication operation can be extended to the set \mathbb{R}_X of all scalars letting $s \cdot 0 = 0 = 0 \cdot s$ for all scalars $s \in \mathbb{R}_X$. The operation of addition on \mathbb{R}_X is defined with the help of the unary operation

$$1- : \mathbb{R}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_X, \quad 1- : \overrightarrow{ove} \mapsto \overrightarrow{ev\dot{o}},$$

called the *01-involution*. For every $y \in \mathbb{R}_X \setminus \{1\}$, let $-y := (1-y) \cdot (1-(1-y)^{-1})$ be the additive inverse of y in \mathbb{R}_X . The additive inverse -1 to 1 is defined as the unique element of the set $\mathbb{R}_X \setminus \{y \cdot (1-y^{-1}) : y \in \mathbb{R}_X^*\}$. The operation of addition $+ : \mathbb{R}_X \times \mathbb{R}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_X$, $+ : (x, y) \mapsto x + y$, is defined by the formula

$$x + y := \begin{cases} y & \text{if } x = 0; \\ x \cdot (1 - (x^{-1} \cdot (-y))) & \text{if } x \neq 0. \end{cases}$$

By [1, 16.10.2], for every affine space X , the algebraic structure $(\mathbb{R}_X, +, \cdot, 0, 1)$ is a corps, called the *scalar corps* of the affine space X .

Let us recall that a *corps* is a set R endowed with two binary operations $+, \cdot : R \times R \rightarrow R$ and two distinct constants $0, 1 \in R$ that satisfy the following axioms:

- (1) $\forall x, y, z \in F \quad x + (y + z) = (x + y) + z;$
- (2) $\forall x, y \in F \quad x + y = y + x;$
- (3) $\forall x \in F \quad x + 0 = x = 0 + x;$
- (4) $\forall x \in F \exists y \in F \quad x + y = 0 = y + x;$
- (5) $\forall x, y, z \in F \quad x \cdot (y \cdot z) = (x \cdot y) \cdot z;$
- (6) $\forall x \in F \quad x \cdot 1 = x = 1 \cdot x;$
- (7) $\forall x \in F \setminus \{0\} \exists y \in F \quad x \cdot y = 1 = y \cdot x;$
- (8) $\forall a, x, y \in F \quad a \cdot (x + y) = a \cdot x + a \cdot y;$
- (9) $\forall a, x, y \in F \quad (x + y) \cdot a = x \cdot a + y \cdot a.$

A corps F is called a *field* if $x \cdot y = y \cdot x$ for all $x, y \in F$.

An *R-module* over a corps R is a nonempty set \mathbf{X} endowed with binary operations

$$+ : \mathbf{X} \times \mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{X}, \quad + : (x, y) \mapsto x + y, \quad \text{and} \quad \cdot : R \times \mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{X}, \quad \cdot : (\alpha, x) \mapsto \alpha \cdot x,$$

that satisfy the axioms:

- (1) $\forall x, y, z \in \mathbf{X} \quad (x + y) + z = x + (y + z);$
- (2) $\forall x, y \in \mathbf{X} \quad 0 \cdot x = 0 \cdot y;$
- (3) $\forall \alpha, \beta \in R \forall x \in \mathbf{X} \quad \alpha \cdot (\beta \cdot x) = (\alpha \cdot \beta) \cdot x;$
- (4) $\forall x \in \mathbf{X} \quad 1 \cdot x = x;$
- (5) $\forall \alpha, \beta \in R \forall x \in \mathbf{X} \quad (\alpha + \beta) \cdot x = \alpha \cdot x + \beta \cdot x;$
- (6) $\forall \alpha \in R \forall x, y \in \mathbf{X} \quad \alpha \cdot (x + y) = \alpha \cdot x + \alpha \cdot y.$

Modules over fields are also called *vector spaces* over fields.

2. PROJECTIVE EQUIVALENCE OF LINE QUADRUPLES

By analogy with affine spaces X which possess the canonical corps of scalars \mathbb{R}_X , projective spaces possess a canonical field of proscalars \mathbb{F}_X , defined and studied in this section. Proscalars in projective spaces will be defined as equivalence classes of Pappian line quadruples.

Definition 2.1. A *line quadruple* in a projective space X is a quadruple $zvui \in X^4$ such that $|\{z, v, u, i\}| = 2$ and $|\{z, u, i\}| = 3$.

For a projective space X , by $\overset{\cdot\cdot\cdot}{X}$ we denote the set of line quadruples in X .

In a line quadruple $zvui$, the points z, v, u, i play non-symmetric roles. The notations z, v, u, i are abbreviations of *zero, variable, unit, infinity*, respectively.

Observe that every quadruple $zvui \in X^4$ in a set X is a function $zvui : 4 \rightarrow X$. So we can consider its composition $Fzvui$ with any other function F . This composition is a quadruple if and only if $\{z, v, u, i\} \subseteq \text{dom}[F]$.

Example 2.2. Every line quadruple $zvui$ in a Steiner projective space X is equal to $zzui$, $zuui$, or $ziui$.

Definition 2.3. Given two line quadruples $zvui, oxej \in \overset{\cdot\cdot\cdot}{X}$ in a projective space X , we write $zvui \not\asymp oxej$ and say that the line quadruples $zvui, oxej$ are *projectively equivalent* if there exists a line projectivity P in X such that $Pzvui = oxej$.

The following proposition shows that the projective equivalence is indeed an equivalence on the set of line quadruples in a projective space.

Proposition 2.4 ([1, 23.1.4]). *Let $zvui, \hat{z}\hat{v}\hat{u}\hat{i}, \check{z}\check{v}\check{u}\check{i}$ be three line quadruples in a projective space X . Then*

- (1) $zvui \not\asymp zvui$;
- (2) $\hat{z}\hat{v}\hat{u}\hat{i} \not\asymp \check{z}\check{v}\check{u}\check{i} \Rightarrow \check{z}\check{v}\check{u}\check{i} \not\asymp \hat{z}\hat{v}\hat{u}\hat{i}$;
- (3) $(\hat{z}\hat{v}\hat{u}\hat{i} \not\asymp zvui \wedge zvui \not\asymp \check{z}\check{v}\check{u}\check{i}) \Rightarrow \check{z}\check{v}\check{u}\check{i} \not\asymp \hat{z}\hat{v}\hat{u}\hat{i}$.

A triple of points $xyz \in X^3$ in a liner X is called a *colinear triple* if the points x, y, z are distinct and belong to some line.

Corollary 2.5 ([1, 23.1.5]). *For every line quadruple $zvui \in \overset{\cdot\cdot\cdot}{X}$ in a (Pappian) projective space X and any colinear triple $oej \in X^3$ there exists a (unique) point $x \in X$ such that $oxej \not\asymp zvui$.*

3. PAPPIAN QUADRUPLES IN PROJECTIVE SPACES

Corollary 2.5 motivates the following definition of a Pappian quadruple.

Definition 3.1. A line quadruple $zvui \in \overset{\cdot\cdot\cdot}{X}$ in a projective space X is called *Pappian* if for every colinear triple $oej \in X^3$ there exists a unique point $x \in X$ such that $oxej \not\asymp zvui$.

Proposition 3.2 ([1, 23.2.2]). *For a line quadruple $zvui \in \overset{\cdot\cdot\cdot}{X}$ in a projective space X , the following statements are equivalent:*

- (1) *the line quadruple $zvui$ is Pappian;*
- (2) *there exists a unique point $x \in X$ such that $xzui \not\asymp zvui$;*
- (3) *for every line projectivity P with $Pzui = zui$ we have $P(v) = v$.*

Corollary 3.3 ([1, 23.2.3]). *For every colinear triple $zui \in X^3$ in a projective space X and every point $v \in \{z, u, i\}$, the line quadruple $zvui$ is Pappian.*

Remark 3.4. Every line quadruple $zvui$ in a Steiner projective space is Pappian.

Corollary 3.5 ([1, 23.2.5]). *A projective space X is Pappian if and only if every line quadruple in X is Pappian.*

Remark 3.6. It can be shown that for any projectively equivalent line quadruples $zvui$ and $oxej$, the line quadruple $zvui$ is Pappian if and only if $oxej$ is Pappian.

Proposition 3.7 ([1, 23.2.7]). *If $zvui$ is a Pappian quadruple in a projective space X , then*

- (1) *the line quadruple $wvzi$ is Pappian.*
- (2) *If $v \notin \{z, i\}$, then the line quadruple $zvui$ is Pappian.*

Corollary 3.8 ([1, 23.2.8]). *Let $zvui$ be a Pappian line quadruple in a projective space X . If $v \notin \{z, u, i\}$, then for every points $a, b, c, d \in X$ with $\{a, b, c, d\} = \{z, v, u, i\}$, the line quadruple $abcd$ is Pappian.*

4. PROPORTIONS AND PROSCALARS IN PROJECTIVE SPACES

By Proposition 2.4, the relation of projective equivalence \approx is an equivalence relation on the set $\overset{\dots}{X}$ of all line quadruples in X . So, we can consider the quotient set $\overset{\dots}{X}_{\approx}$ of $\overset{\dots}{X}$ by the equivalence relation \approx . Elements of the set $\overset{\dots}{X}_{\approx}$ are called *proportions*² in X .

Definition 4.1. For a line quadruple $zvui \in \overset{\dots}{X}$ in a projective space X , its *proportion* is the set

$$\overrightarrow{zvui} := \{xyzj \in \overset{\dots}{X} : xyzj \approx zvui\} \in \overset{\dots}{X}_{\approx}.$$

Corollary 2.5 implies the following existence result.

Corollary 4.2 ([1, 23.3.2]). *Let X be a (Pappian) projective space. For every colinear triple zui in X and every proportion $\alpha \in \overset{\dots}{X}_{\approx}$ there exists a (unique) point $v \in X$ such that $zvui \in \alpha$.*

Definition 4.3. Let X be a projective space. A proportion $\alpha \in \overset{\dots}{X}_{\approx}$ is called a *proscalar* if $\alpha = \overrightarrow{zvui}$ for some (equivalently, every) Pappian line quadruple $zvui \in \overset{\dots}{X}$. The set of all proscalars in a projective space X is denoted by $\overline{\mathbb{F}}_X$.

The set of proscalars $\overline{\mathbb{F}}_X$ is a subset of the set $\overset{\dots}{X}_{\approx}$ on proportions. By Corollary 3.5, a projective space is Pappian if and only if $\overline{\mathbb{F}}_X = \overset{\dots}{X}_{\approx}$.

Example 4.4. For every projective space X , the sets

$$0 := \{zvui \in \overset{\dots}{X} : v = z\}, \quad 1 := \{zvui \in \overset{\dots}{X} : v = u\}, \quad \text{and} \quad \infty := \{zvui \in \overset{\dots}{X} : v = i\}$$

are proscalars and hence $0, 1, \infty$ are elements of the set of $\overline{\mathbb{F}}_X \subseteq \overset{\dots}{X}_{\approx}$.

Example 4.5. Every Steiner projective space X has $\overline{\mathbb{F}}_X = \overset{\dots}{X}_{\approx} = \{0, 1, \infty\}$.

The set of proscalars $\overline{\mathbb{F}}_X$ of a projective space X contains two important subsets:

$$\mathbb{F}_X := \overline{\mathbb{F}}_X \setminus \{\infty\}, \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbb{F}_X^* := \overline{\mathbb{F}}_X \setminus \{0\} = \overline{\mathbb{F}}_X \setminus \{0, \infty\}.$$

The sets \mathbb{F}_X and \mathbb{F}_X^* consist of finite proscalars and finite nonzero proscalars, respectively.

The set \mathbb{F}_X^* of nonzero finite proscalars is a subset of the set

$$\overset{\dots}{X}_{\approx}^* := \overset{\dots}{X}_{\approx} \setminus \{0, \infty\}$$

of all nonzero finite proportions.

5. THE INVERSION AND 01-INVOLUTION OF PROPORTIONS

In this section we consider two natural unary operations on the set of proportions of a projective space. Those two operations are induced by suitable permutations of line quadruples.

Proposition 5.1 ([1, 23.4.1]). *For every projective space X , there exists a unique unary operation*

$$(\cdot)^{-1} : \overset{\dots}{X}_{\approx} \rightarrow \overset{\dots}{X}_{\approx}, \quad (\cdot)^{-1} : p \mapsto p^{-1},$$

such that $0^{-1} = \infty$, $\infty^{-1} = 0$, and $(\overrightarrow{zvui})^{-1} = \overrightarrow{zuvi}$ for every line quadruple $zvui \in \overset{\dots}{X}$ with $v \notin \{z, i\}$.

Definition 5.2. The unary operation $(\cdot)^{-1}$ on $\overset{\dots}{X}_{\approx}$ (resp. $\overline{\mathbb{F}}_X$) introduced in Proposition 5.1 is called the *operation of inversion* of the set of proportions (resp. proscalars) on X .

Propositions 5.1 and 3.7(2) imply the following corollary.

Corollary 5.3 ([1, 23.4.3]). *Let X be a projective space. The operation of inversion on the set $\overline{\mathbb{F}}_X$ has the following properties:*

- (1) $(p^{-1})^{-1} = p$ for every $p \in \overset{\dots}{X}_{\approx}$;
- (2) for every proscalar $p \in \overline{\mathbb{F}}_X$ its inverse p^{-1} is a proscalar.

²Abbreviated from “projective portions”.

By Corollary 5.3(2), the operation of inversion is an involution³ on the sets $\ddot{X}_{\overline{\mathbb{F}}}$ and $\overline{\mathbb{F}}_X$. It can be shown that $[\mathbb{F}_X^*]^{-1} = \mathbb{F}_X^*$ and $[\ddot{X}_{\overline{\mathbb{F}}}^*]^{-1} = \ddot{X}_{\overline{\mathbb{F}}}^*$ for every projective space X .

The definition of the proscalars $0, 1, \infty$ and Corollary 3.8 imply that the following proposition.

Proposition 5.4 ([1, 23.4.5]). *For every projective space X , there exists a unique unary operation*

$$1- : \ddot{X}_{\overline{\mathbb{F}}} \rightarrow \ddot{X}_{\overline{\mathbb{F}}}, \quad 1- : p \mapsto 1-p,$$

such that

- (1) $1-zvui = uvzi$ for every line quadruple $zvui \in \ddot{X}$;
- (2) $1-(1-p) = p$ for every proportion $p \in \ddot{X}_{\overline{\mathbb{F}}}$;
- (3) $1-0 = 1, 1-1 = 0, 1-\infty = \infty$;
- (4) for every proscalar $p \in \overline{\mathbb{F}}_X$, the proportion $1-p$ is a proscalar.

This unary operation is called the **01-involution** of the set of proportions.

By Corollary 3.8, for every Pappian line quadruple $abcd$ consisting of 4 distinct points of a projective space, every permutation of this quadruple remain a Pappian quadruple. It truns out that among 24 possible permutations of the Pappian quadruple $abcd$, there are only six distinct proscalars.

Theorem 5.5 ([1, 23.8.1]). *For every Pappian line quadruple $zvui$ with $v \notin \{z, i\}$ in a projective space X , the quadruples $vuzi$, $zuvi$ and $iuvz$ are Pappian and*

$$\overrightarrow{vuzi} = 1-\overrightarrow{zvui}, \quad \overrightarrow{zuvi} = (\overrightarrow{zvui})^{-1}, \quad \overrightarrow{iuvz} = \overrightarrow{zvui}.$$

Corollary 5.6 ([1, 23.8.6]). *Let a, b, c, d be four distinct points in a projective space X . If the quadruple $abcd$ is Pappian, then for the proscalar $\lambda := \overrightarrow{abcd} \in \overline{\mathbb{F}}_X \setminus \{0, 1, \infty\}$ we have the following identities:*

$$\begin{aligned} \overrightarrow{abcd} &= \overrightarrow{badc} = \overrightarrow{cdab} = \overrightarrow{dcba} = \lambda \\ \overrightarrow{acbd} &= \overrightarrow{bdac} = \overrightarrow{cadb} = \overrightarrow{dbca} = \lambda^{-1} \\ \overrightarrow{cbad} &= \overrightarrow{dabc} = \overrightarrow{adcb} = \overrightarrow{bcda} = 1-\lambda \\ \overrightarrow{bcad} &= \overrightarrow{adbc} = \overrightarrow{dacb} = \overrightarrow{bdca} = 1-\lambda^{-1} \\ \overrightarrow{bacd} &= \overrightarrow{abdc} = \overrightarrow{dcab} = \overrightarrow{bcd a} = (1-\lambda^{-1})^{-1} \\ \overrightarrow{cabd} &= \overrightarrow{dbac} = \overrightarrow{acdb} = \overrightarrow{bdca} = (1-\lambda)^{-1}. \end{aligned}$$

6. MULTIPLICATION OF PROPORTIONS AND PROSCALARS

In this section we introduce and study the binary operation of multiplication of proportions and proscalars. We start with multiplication of nonzero finite proportions and proscalars.

Theorem 6.1 ([1, 23.5.1]). *For every projective space X , there exists a binary operation*

$$\cdot : \text{dom}[\cdot] \rightarrow \ddot{X}_{\overline{\mathbb{F}}}^*, \quad \cdot : (\alpha, \beta) \mapsto \alpha \cdot \beta, \quad \text{on the set } \text{dom}[\cdot] = (\mathbb{F}_X^* \times \ddot{X}_{\overline{\mathbb{F}}}^*) \cup (\ddot{X}_{\overline{\mathbb{F}}}^* \times \mathbb{F}_X^*),$$

which is uniquely determined by the condition

- (1) $\forall (\alpha, \beta) \in \text{dom}[\cdot] \quad \forall z, a, b, u, i \in X \quad (zabi \in \alpha \wedge zbui \in \beta) \Rightarrow (zau i \in \alpha \cdot \beta)$.

The binary operation \cdot has the following properties for every proportions $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \ddot{X}_{\overline{\mathbb{F}}}^*$:

- (2) $1 \cdot \alpha = \alpha = \alpha \cdot 1$;
- (3) if $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}_X^*$, then $\alpha \cdot \beta = \beta \cdot \alpha$;
- (4) if $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}_X^*$, then $\alpha \cdot \alpha^{-1} = 1 = \alpha^{-1} \cdot \alpha$;
- (5) if $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{F}_X^*$, then $\alpha \cdot \beta \in \mathbb{F}_X^*$;
- (6) if $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{F}_X^*$, then $(\alpha \cdot \beta) \cdot \gamma = \alpha \cdot (\beta \cdot \gamma)$.

³A self-map $F : X \rightarrow X$ of a set X is an **involution** if $F(F(x)) = x$ for every $x \in X$.

Corollary 6.2 ([1, 23.5.2]). *For every projective space X , the set \mathbb{F}_X^* is a commutative group with respect to the binary operation $\cdot : \mathbb{F}_X^* \times \mathbb{F}_X^* \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_X^*$, defined by the formula:*

$$\forall \alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{F}_X^* \quad \forall z, a, b, u, i \in X \quad (zabi \in \alpha \wedge zbui \in \beta) \Rightarrow zauri \in \alpha \cdot \beta.$$

For a projective space X , it is natural to extend the multiplication operation from the commutative group \mathbb{F}_X^* to the set of all finite proscalars $\mathbb{F}_X = \mathbb{F}_X^* \cup \{0\}$ letting $0 \cdot \alpha = 0 = \alpha \cdot 0$ for all $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}_X$. Then \mathbb{F}_X became a commutative monoid with zero, containing \mathbb{F}_X^* as a subgroup.

We can also extend the multiplicative operation further on to the set $\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$ of all proscalars letting

$$\infty \cdot 0 = 1 = 0 \cdot \infty \quad \text{and} \quad \forall \alpha \in \bar{\mathbb{F}}_X \setminus \{0\} \quad (\alpha \cdot \infty = \infty = \infty \cdot \alpha).$$

Then $\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$ is a commutative unital magma such that $\alpha \cdot \alpha^{-1} = 1 = \alpha^{-1} \cdot \alpha$ for all $\alpha \in \bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$. The subset $\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X \setminus \{0\}$ of $\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$ is a commutative monoid, isomorphic to the commutative monoid \mathbb{F}_X . However, the magma $\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$ is not a semigroup because its binary operation is not associative:

$$(0 \cdot 0) \cdot \infty = 0 \cdot \infty = 1 \neq 0 = 0 \cdot 1 = 0 \cdot (0 \cdot \infty).$$

On the other hand, for every $\alpha, \gamma \in \bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$ and $\beta \in \mathbb{F}_X^*$ the associative law $(\alpha \cdot \beta) \cdot \gamma = \alpha \cdot (\beta \cdot \gamma)$ does hold.

7. PROSCALARS VERSUS SCALARS

In this section we study the interplay between scalars in an affine space and proscalars in its projective completion.

Lemma 7.1 ([1, 23.6.3]). *Let X be a projective completion of an affine space A , $H := X \setminus A$ be the horizon of A in X , and $\ddot{X}_A := \ddot{X} \cap (A^3 \times H)$. For every Pappian quadruple $zvui \in \ddot{X}_A$, the triple zvu is Desarguesian in the affine space A . Moreover, for any Pappian quadruples $\hat{z}\hat{v}\hat{u}\hat{i}$, $\check{z}\check{v}\check{u}\check{i} \in \ddot{X}_A$ with $\hat{z}\hat{v}\hat{u}\hat{i} \not\asymp \check{z}\check{v}\check{u}\check{i}$ we have $\hat{z}\hat{v}\hat{u} \bowtie \check{z}\check{v}\check{u}$.*

Let X be a projective completion of an affine space A and let $H := X \setminus A$ be the horizon of A in X . By [1, 8.3.19], H is a hyperplane in X . Consider the set of line quadruples

$$\ddot{X}_A := \ddot{X} \cap (A^3 \times H) = \{zvui \in \ddot{X} : z, v, u \in A, i \in H\}.$$

Consider the map $\Psi_A : \mathbb{F}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_A$ assigning to every finite proscalar $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}_X$ the scalar \overrightarrow{zau} where $zauri$ is any line quadruple in $\alpha \cap \ddot{X}_A$ (such a line quadruple $zauri$ exists, by Corollary 2.5). Lemma 7.1 ensures that the value $\Psi_A(\alpha) = \overrightarrow{zau}$ does not depend on the choice of the line quadruple $zauri \in \alpha \cap \ddot{X}_A$. Therefore, $\Psi_A : \mathbb{F}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_A$ is a well-defined function.

Theorem 7.2 ([1, 23.6.4]). *For any projective completion X of an affine space A , the function $\Psi_A : \mathbb{F}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_A$ has the following properties:*

- (1) Ψ_A is injective;
- (2) $\Psi_A(0) = 0$ and $\Psi_A(1) = 1$;
- (3) $\Psi_A(\alpha \cdot \beta) = \Psi_A(\alpha) \cdot \Psi_A(\beta)$ for any proscalars $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{F}_X$;
- (4) $\Psi_A(1 - \alpha) = 1 - \Psi_A(\alpha)$ for every proscalar $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}_X$;
- (5) $\Psi_A[\mathbb{F}_X] \subseteq \mathcal{Z}(\mathbb{R}_X) := \{\alpha \in \mathbb{R}_A : \forall \beta \in \mathbb{R}_A \quad (\alpha \cdot \beta = \beta \cdot \alpha)\}$.

In light of Theorem 7.2(5) it is natural to ask whether $\Psi_A[\mathbb{F}_X] = \mathcal{Z}(\mathbb{R}_A)$ for any projective completion X of an affine space A . In general, the answer to this question is negative: there exists a non-Desarguesian Thalesian affine plane A of order 9 such that $\mathcal{Z}(\mathbb{R}_A) = \mathbb{R}_A = \{0, 1, 2\}$ but $\mathbb{F}_X = \{0, 1\}$ for every projective completion X of A , see Remark 23.6.13 in [1]. On the other hand, for Desarguesian affine spaces, we have the following theorem.

Theorem 7.3 ([1, 23.6.11]). *If X is a projective completion X of a Desarguesian affine space A , then $\Psi_A[\mathbb{F}_X] = \mathcal{Z}(\mathbb{R}_A)$.*

Corollary 7.4 ([1, 23.6.12]). *If a projective space X has $\mathbb{F}_X \neq \{0, 1\}$, then X is Moufang.*

8. ADDITION OF PROSCALARS

In this section we shall prove that for every projective space X the operations of multiplication and 01-involution on the set of finite proscalars \mathbb{F}_X induce a unique operation of addition that turns \mathbb{F}_X into a field. Let us recall that the 01-involution $1- : \overline{\mathbb{F}}_X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{F}}_X$ assigns to every proscalar \overrightarrow{zvu} the proscalar $1-\overrightarrow{zvu} := \overrightarrow{uvz}$.

Theorem 8.1 ([1, 23.7.1]). *For every projective space X , there exists a unique binary operation $+ : \mathbb{F}_X \times \mathbb{F}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_X$ such that $(\mathbb{F}_X, +, \cdot, 0, 1)$ is a field, and $1-\alpha = 1 - \alpha$ for every finite proscalar $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}_X$.*

Definition 8.2. For every projective space X , the set \mathbb{F}_X of finite proscalars endowed with the binary operations of addition and multiplication of scalars is called the *proscalar field* of X . For a completely regular space X , its proscalar field \mathbb{F}_X is defined as the proscalar field $\overline{\mathbb{F}}_{\overline{X}}$ of the spread completion \overline{X} of X .

Corollary 8.3 ([1, 23.7.3]). *For every projective completion X of a Desarguesian affine space A , the function $\Psi_A : \mathbb{F}_X \rightarrow \mathcal{Z}(\mathbb{R}_A)$ is an isomorphism of the fields \mathbb{F}_X and $\mathcal{Z}(\mathbb{R}_A)$.*

At the moment, for every projective space X , we have defined the multiplicative operation on the whole set of proscalars $\overline{\mathbb{F}}_X$, but the additive operation is defined only on the set \mathbb{F}_X of finite proscalars. The additive operation can be extended to the whole set $\overline{\mathbb{F}}_X$ letting

$$\infty + \infty := 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \infty + \alpha = \alpha + \infty := \infty \quad \text{for all } \alpha \in \mathbb{F}_X.$$

The set of proscalars $\overline{\mathbb{F}}_X$ endowed with the extended addition and multiplication operations is called the *proscalar profield* of the projective space X . Proscalar profields of projective spaces motivate studying abstract profields and procorps, which will be done in the next section.

9. PROCORPS AND PROFIELDS

Definition 9.1 ([1, 24.1.1]). A *procors* is a set F endowed with two binary operations $+, \cdot : F \times F \rightarrow F$ and three distinct constants $0, 1, \infty \in F$ that satisfy the following nine axioms:

- (1) $\forall x, z \in F \forall y \in F \setminus \{\infty\} \quad (x + (y + z) = (x + y) + z)$;
- (2) $\forall x \in F \quad (x + 0 = x = 0 + x)$;
- (3) $\forall x \in F \exists y \in F \quad (x + y = 0 = y + x)$;
- (4) $\forall x, z \in F \forall y \in F \setminus \{0, \infty\} \quad (x \cdot (y \cdot z) = (x \cdot y) \cdot z)$;
- (5) $\forall x \in F \quad (x \cdot 1 = x = 1 \cdot x)$;
- (6) $\forall x \in F \exists y \in F \quad (x \cdot y = 1 = y \cdot x)$;
- (7) $\forall a \in F \setminus \{0, \infty\} \forall x, y \in F \quad (a \cdot (x + y) = a \cdot x + a \cdot y)$;
- (8) $\forall x, y \in F \forall b \in F \setminus \{0, \infty\} \quad ((x + y) \cdot b = x \cdot b + y \cdot b)$;
- (9) $0 \cdot 0 = 0, \infty \cdot \infty = \infty$ and $1 + \infty = \infty = \infty + 1$.

A procors F is called a *proffield* if $x \cdot y = y \cdot x$ for all elements $x, y \in F$.

Example 9.2. For every projective space X its proscalar profield $\overline{\mathbb{F}}_X$ is a proffield.

Example 9.3. Given any corps F , and any element $\infty \notin F$, consider the set $\overline{F} := F \cup \{\infty\}$, and extend the operations of addition and multiplication from F to \overline{F} letting

$$\begin{aligned} \infty + \infty &= 0, \quad \infty \cdot 0 = 1 = 0 \cdot \infty, \\ \forall x \in \overline{F} \setminus \{\infty\} \quad (x + \infty &= \infty = \infty + x), \\ \forall x \in \overline{F} \setminus \{0\} \quad (x \cdot \infty &= \infty = \infty \cdot x). \end{aligned}$$

It can be shown that \overline{F} is a procors. This procors is called the *projective ∞ -extension* of the corps F . If F is a field, then its projective ∞ -extension is a proffield.

The following theorem shows that procors are exactly projective ∞ -extensions of corps.

Theorem 9.4 ([1, 24.1.4]). *For every procors \overline{F} , the set $F := \overline{F} \setminus \{\infty\}$ endowed with the induced operations of addition and multiplication is a corps and \overline{F} is the projective ∞ -extension of F .*

Example 9.5 ([1, 24.1.19]). The 3-element set $\bar{F}_3 := \{0, 1, \infty\}$, endowed with the addition and multiplication operations, defined by the following addition and multiplication tables

$$\begin{array}{c|ccc} + & 0 & 1 & \infty \\ \hline 0 & 0 & 1 & \infty \\ 1 & 1 & \infty & 0 \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & 1 \end{array} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{array}{c|ccc} \cdot & 0 & 1 & \infty \\ \hline 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & \infty \\ \infty & 1 & \infty & \infty \end{array}$$

satisfies all the axioms of a profield except for the equality $1 + \infty = \infty$ in the last axiom. The additive operation on \bar{F}_3 is associative, so $(\bar{F}_3, +)$ is a group.

Example 9.6 ([1, 24.1.20]). The 4-element set $\bar{F}_4 := \{0, 1, \infty, 1+\infty\}$, endowed with the addition and multiplication operations, defined by the following addition and multiplication tables

$$\begin{array}{c|cccc} + & 0 & 1 & \infty & 1+\infty \\ \hline 0 & 0 & 1 & \infty & 1+\infty \\ 1 & 1 & \infty & 1+\infty & 0 \\ \infty & \infty & 1+\infty & 0 & 1 \\ 1+\infty & 1+\infty & 0 & 1 & \infty \end{array} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{array}{c|cccc} \cdot & 0 & 1 & \infty & 1+\infty \\ \hline 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & \infty & 1+\infty \\ \infty & 1 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ 1+\infty & 0 & 1+\infty & \infty & 1 \end{array}$$

satisfies all the axioms of a profield except for the equality $1 + \infty = \infty$ in the last axiom. The additive operation on \bar{F}_4 is associative, so $(\bar{F}_4, +)$ is a cyclic group.

Example 9.7 ([1, 24.1.21]). Consider the 4-element set $\bar{B}_4 := \{0, 1, \infty, 1+\infty\}$, endowed with the addition and multiplication operations, defined by the following addition and multiplication tables

$$\begin{array}{c|cccc} + & 0 & 1 & \infty & 1+\infty \\ \hline 0 & 0 & 1 & \infty & 1+\infty \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 1+\infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 1+\infty & 0 & 1 \\ 1+\infty & 1+\infty & \infty & 1 & 0 \end{array} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{array}{c|cccc} \cdot & 0 & 1 & \infty & 1+\infty \\ \hline 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & \infty & 1+\infty \\ \infty & 1 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ 1+\infty & 0 & 1+\infty & \infty & 1 \end{array}$$

satisfies all the axioms of a profield except for the equality $1 + \infty = \infty$ in the last axiom. The additive operation on \bar{B}_4 is associative, and $(\bar{B}_4, +)$ is a Boolean group.

Theorem 9.8 ([1, 24.1.22]). *The operation of addition in a procorps F is uniquely determined by the unary operation of 01-involution $1- : F \rightarrow F$, $1- : x \mapsto 1-x$ and the operation of multiplication in the group $F^* := F \setminus \{0, \infty\}$.*

10. MÖBIUS TRANSFORMATIONS OF PROFIELDS

In this section we study Möbius transformations of profields.

Definition 10.1. Let \bar{F} is a profield, $F := \bar{F} \setminus \{\infty\}$ and $F^* := F \setminus \{0\}$. A bijective function $\mu : \bar{F} \rightarrow \bar{F}$ is a *Möbius transformation* of \bar{F} if there exist elements $a \in F^*$, $b, c \in F$ and a sign $\pm 1 \in \{-1, +1\}$ such that $\mu(x) = a \cdot (x + b)^{\pm 1} + c$ for all $x \in \bar{F}$.

In Definition 10.1 we assume that for every element $x \in \bar{F}$, $x^{+1} = x$, and x^{-1} is the unique element such that $x \cdot x^{-1} = 1 = x^{-1} \cdot x$. For example, $\infty^{+1} = \infty$ and $\infty^{-1} = 0$.

Exercise 10.2. Show that $(x \cdot y)^{-1} = y^{-1} \cdot x^{-1}$ for every elements x, y of a procorps.

Proposition 10.3 ([1, 24.2.3]). *The set of Möbius transformations of a profield \bar{F} is a subgroup of the permutation group of the profield \bar{F} .*

Theorem 10.4 ([1, 24.2.4]). *Two Möbius transformations $\mu, \eta : \bar{F} \rightarrow \bar{F}$ of a profield \bar{F} coincide if and only if $\mu|_{\{0,1,\infty\}} = \eta|_{\{0,1,\infty\}}$.*

Theorem 10.5 ([1, 24.2.5]). *For every distinct elements z, u, i of a profield \bar{F} , there exists a unique Möbius transformation $\mu : \bar{F} \rightarrow \bar{F}$ such that $\mu(0) = z$, $\mu(1) = u$, and $\mu(i) = \infty$.*

11. COORDINATE CHARTS ON LINES IN PAPPIAN PROJECTIVE SPACES

Let L be a line in a projective space X . Given any distinct points $z, u, i \in L$, consider the function

$$\phi_{zui} : L \rightarrow \overset{\dots}{\bar{X}}_{\neq}, \quad \phi_{zui} : x \mapsto \overrightarrow{zxui},$$

assigning to every point $x \in L$ the proportion \overrightarrow{zxui} . Corollary 2.5 implies that the function $\phi_{zui} : L \rightarrow \overset{\dots}{\bar{X}}_{\neq}$ is surjective. If the projective space X is Pappian, then $\overset{\dots}{\bar{X}}_{\neq} = \bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$ and the function $\phi_{zui} : L \rightarrow \bar{\mathbb{F}}_X = \overset{\dots}{\bar{X}}_{\neq}$ is bijective, by Corollary 4.2. In this case the function $\phi_{zui} : L \rightarrow \bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$ is called a *coordinate chart* on the projective line L . The coordinate chart ϕ_{zui} identifies the projective line L with the proscalar profield $\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$. Under this identification, we have

$$\phi_{zui}(z) = \overrightarrow{zzui} = 0, \quad \phi_{zui}(u) = \overrightarrow{zuiu} = 1, \quad \text{and} \quad \phi_{zui}(i) = \overrightarrow{ziui} = \infty.$$

For six points $z, u, i, o, e, j \in L$ with $|\{z, u, i\}| = 3 = |\{o, e, j\}|$, the bijective function

$$\phi_{zui} \circ \phi_{oej}^{-1} : \bar{\mathbb{F}}_X \rightarrow \bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$$

is called the *transition function* between the charts ϕ_{oej} and ϕ_{zui} .

$$\begin{array}{ccc} & L & \\ \phi_{oej} \swarrow & & \searrow \phi_{zui} \\ \bar{\mathbb{F}}_X & \xrightarrow{\phi_{zui} \circ \phi_{oej}^{-1}} & \bar{\mathbb{F}}_X \end{array}$$

The following theorem shows that the transition functions are Möbius transformations of the proscalar profield $\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$.

Theorem 11.1 ([1, 24.3.3]). *Let L be a line in a projective space X and $z, u, i, o, e, j \in L$ be points such that $|\{z, u, i\}| = 3 = |\{o, e, j\}|$. The transition function $\phi_{oej} \circ \phi_{zui}^{-1}$ is a Möbius transformation of the proscalar profield $\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$.*

Theorem 11.1 implies the following coordinate description of line projectivities in Pappian projective spaces.

Theorem 11.2 ([1, 24.3.5]). *Let L, Λ be two lines in a Pappian projective space, and $z, u, i \in L, o, e, j \in \Lambda$ be points such that $|\{z, u, i\}| = 3 = |\{o, e, j\}|$. A function $F : L \rightarrow \Lambda$ is a line projectivity if and only if the function $\phi_{oej} \circ F \circ \phi_{zui}^{-1}$ is a Möbius transformation of the proscalar profield $\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$.*

12. PROJECTIVITIES, PROPORTIONALITIES, AND PROSCALARITIES

Definition 12.1. An automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a projective space X is called

- a *projectivity* if for every line $L \subseteq X$, the restriction $A|_L$ is a line projectivity;
- a *proportionality* if for every line quadruple $zvui \in \overset{\dots}{\bar{X}}$ we have $Azvui \neq zvui$;
- a *proscalarity* if for every Pappian line quadruple $zvui \in \overset{\dots}{\bar{X}}$ we have $Azvui \neq zvui$.

Proposition 12.2 ([1, 24.4.2]). *For any automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a projective space X , the following conditions hold.*

- (1) *If A is a projectivity, then A is proportionality.*
- (2) *If A is a proportionality, then A is a proscalarity.*

Therefore, for every automorphism of a projective spaces, we have the implications:

$$\text{projectivity} \Rightarrow \text{proportionality} \Rightarrow \text{proscalarity}.$$

For Pappian projective spaces, those three notions are equivalent.

Theorem 12.3 ([1, 24.4.3]). *For any automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a Pappian projective space X , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) *A is a projectivity;*
- (2) *A is a proportionality;*
- (3) *A is a proscalarity.*

Definition 12.4. An automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a Pappian projective space X is called *projective* if A satisfies the equivalent conditions of Theorem 12.3.

For a projective space X , let $\text{Proj}(X)$, $\text{Proj}_P(X)$, $\text{Aff}_S(X)$ be the subsets of the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$, consisting of all projectivities, proportionalities, and proscalarities, respectively. Proposition 12.2 and Theorem 12.3 imply the following corollary.

Corollary 12.5 ([1, 24.4.5]). *For every projective space X , the sets $\text{Proj}(X)$, $\text{Proj}_P(X)$, $\text{Proj}_S(X)$ are normal subgroups of the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$ such that $\text{Proj}(X) \subseteq \text{Proj}_P(X) \subseteq \text{Proj}_S(X)$. If the projective space X is Pappian, then $\text{Proj}(X) = \text{Proj}_P(X) = \text{Proj}_S(X)$.*

Remark 12.6 ([1, 24.4.6]). By a result of Grundhöfer [7], and P. Müller, G.P. Nagy [8], for every line L in a non-Pappian finite projective space X , the group $\text{Proj}_X(L)$ of line projectivities of the line L is either the symmetric group S_L of L or the alternative group A_L of L . This result implies that $\text{Proj}_P(X) = \text{Proj}_S(X) = \text{Aut}(X)$. Moreover, $\text{Proj}(X) = \text{Aut}(X)$ if $\text{Proj}_X(L) = S_L$.

Let X be a projective space and $\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$ be its proscalar profield. For every automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ and every line quadruple $zvui$ in X , the image $Azvui$ is a line quadruple in X . If the line quadruple $zvui$ is Pappian, then so is the line quadruple $Azvui$. This observation allows us to define the map $\bar{A} : \bar{\mathbb{F}}_X \rightarrow \bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$ assigning to every proscalar $p \in \mathbb{R}_X$ the proscalar $\bar{A}(p) = \{Azvui : zvui \in p\}$. It is easy to see that the function $\bar{A} : \bar{\mathbb{F}}_X \rightarrow \bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$ is an automorphism of the profield $\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$. For two automorphisms $A, B : X \rightarrow X$ and their composition $C = A \circ B$, the automorphism $\bar{C} : \bar{\mathbb{F}}_X \rightarrow \bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$ is equal to the composition $\bar{A} \circ \bar{B}$ of the automorphisms \bar{A}, \bar{B} of the profield $\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$. This means that the correspondence $T : \text{Aut}(X) \rightarrow \text{Aut}(\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X)$, $T : A \mapsto \bar{A}$, is a homomorphism from the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$ of the line X into the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X)$ of the profield $\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$. The definition of a proscalar implies that the automorphism $\bar{A} : \bar{\mathbb{F}}_X \rightarrow \bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$ is the identity map of $\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$ if and only if the automorphism A is a proscalar of X . Let us write down this fact for future references.

Proposition 12.7 ([1, 24.4.8]). *For every projective space X , the function $\text{Aut}(X) \rightarrow \text{Aut}(\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X)$, $A \mapsto \bar{A}$, is a homomorphism from the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$ of the projective space X into the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X)$ of the profield $\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X$. The kernel of the homomorphism $\text{Aut}(X) \rightarrow \text{Aut}(\bar{\mathbb{F}}_X)$ coincides with the group $\text{Proj}_S(X)$ of proscalarities of X .*

13. PROJECTIVE REPERS AND FRAMES IN DESARGUESIAN PROJECTIVE SPACES

In this section we establish some deeper homogeneity properties of Desarguesian projective spaces, using the notion of a projective reper.

Definition 13.1 ([1, 18.8.1]). A *projective reper* in a projective space X is a function $r \subseteq X \times X$ whose domain $\text{dom}[r]$ is a maximal independent set in X containing a unique point $o = r(o)$ such that $r(x) \in \overline{o x} \setminus \{o, x\}$ for every $x \in \text{dom}[r] \setminus \{o\}$. The point o is called the *origin* of the projective reper r .

Proposition 13.2 ([1, 18.8.3]). *Every projective reper r in a projective space X has the following properties:*

- (1) *the function r is injective;*
- (2) *the intersection $\text{dom}[r] \cap \text{rng}[r]$ is a singleton $\{o\}$ containing the origin o of the projective reper r ;*
- (3) *the set $\text{rng}[r]$ is maximal independent in X ;*
- (4) *the function $r^{-1} := \{(y, x) : (x, y) \in r\}$ is a projective reper in X ;*

- (5) the flat $H := \overline{\text{dom}[r] \setminus \text{rng}[r]}$ is a hyperplane in X and the subliner $X \setminus H$ is affine and regular.

Every isomorphism $F : X \rightarrow Y$ between affine spaces X, Y induces an isomorphism $\ddot{F} : \mathbb{R}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_Y$, $\ddot{F} : s \mapsto \{Fxyz : xyz \in \sigma\}$, of the scalar corps \mathbb{R}_X and \mathbb{R}_Y of the affine spaces X and Y .

Theorem 13.3 ([1, 18.8.4]). *Let X, Y be two Desarguesian projective spaces and r, r' be two projective repers in X, Y , respectively. Let $I : \mathbb{R}_A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_B$ be any isomorphism between scalar corps of the affine liners $A := X \setminus \overline{\text{dom}[r] \setminus \text{rng}[r]}$ and $B := Y \setminus \overline{\text{dom}[r'] \setminus \text{rng}[r']}$. For every bijective function $\psi : \text{dom}[r] \cup \text{rng}[r] \rightarrow \text{dom}[r'] \cup \text{rng}[r']$ with $\psi \circ r = r' \circ \psi$, there exists a unique isomorphism $\Phi : X \rightarrow Y$ such that $\psi \subseteq \Phi$, and the restriction $\phi := \Phi|_A$ is an isomorphism between the affine spaces A and B such that $\ddot{\phi} = I$.*

Corollary 13.4 ([1, 18.8.5]). *Let r, r' be two projective repers in a Desarguesian projective space X . Every bijective function $\varphi : \text{dom}[r] \cup \text{rng}[r] \rightarrow \text{dom}[r'] \cup \text{rng}[r']$ with $\varphi \circ r = r' \circ \varphi$ extends to an automorphism $\Phi : X \rightarrow X$.*

For repers in Pappian projective spaces, we have the following sharp results on extension of bejections between repers to isomorphisms of projective spaces.

Corollary 13.5 ([1, 24.5.2]). *Let r be a projective reper in a Pappian projective space X . Two isomorphisms $A, B : X \rightarrow Y$ to a projective space Y coincide if and only if $\ddot{A} = \ddot{B}$ and $A(x) = B(x)$ for every $x \in \text{dom}[r] \cup \text{rng}[r]$.*

Theorem 13.6 ([1, 24.5.3]). *Let X, Y be two Pappian projective spaces and r, r' be two projective repers in X, Y , respectively. For every profield isomorphism $\bar{I} : \mathbb{F}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_Y$ and every bijective function $\varphi : \text{dom}[r] \cup \text{rng}[r] \rightarrow \text{dom}[r'] \cup \text{rng}[r']$ with $\varphi \circ r = r' \circ \varphi$, there exists a unique isomorphism $\Phi : X \rightarrow Y$ such that $\varphi \subseteq \Phi$ and $\ddot{\Phi} = \bar{I}$.*

Corollary 13.7 ([1, 24.5.4]). *Let r, r' be two projective repers in a Pappian projective space X . Every bijective function $\varphi : \text{dom}[r] \cup \text{rng}[r] \rightarrow \text{dom}[r'] \cup \text{rng}[r']$ with $\varphi \circ r = r' \circ \varphi$ extends to a unique projective isomorphism $\Phi : X \rightarrow Y$.*

Definition 13.8 ([1, 18.8.6]). Let X be a projective space of finite rank $\|X\|$. A subset $M \subseteq X$ is called a *projective frame* in X if $|M| = \|X\| + 1$ and for every $x \in M$, the set $M \setminus \{x\}$ is independent in X .

Proposition 13.9 ([1, 18.8.7]). *Let X be a projective space of finite rank and M be a projective frame in X . For every distinct points $o, u \in M$ there exists a projective reper r in X having the following properties:*

- (1) $\text{dom}[r] = M \setminus \{u\}$;
- (2) $r(o) = o$;
- (3) $\{r(e)\} = \overline{o e} \cap \overline{M \setminus \{o, e\}}$ for every point $e \in M \setminus \{o, u\}$;
- (4) $\overline{M \setminus \{o, e\}} = \overline{\{r(e)\} \cup (M \setminus \{o, u, e\})}$ for every point $e \in M \setminus \{o, u\}$;
- (5) $\{u\} = \bigcap_{e \in M \setminus \{o, u\}} \overline{M \setminus \{o, e\}} = \bigcap_{e \in M \setminus \{o, u\}} \overline{\{r(e)\} \cup (M \setminus \{o, u, e\})}$.

The projective reper r is uniquely determined by the properties (1), (2), (3).

Theorem 13.10 ([1, 18.8.8]). *1 Let X be a Desarguesian projective space of finite rank. Every bijection $\varphi : M \rightarrow M'$ between projective frames M, M' in X extends to an automorphism $\Phi : X \rightarrow X$ of X .*

Theorem 13.11 ([1, 24.5.6]). *Let X, Y be two Pappian projective spaces of finite rank $\|X\| = \|Y\|$ and M, M' be two projective frames in the projective spaces X, Y , respectively. For every profield isomorphism $\bar{I} : \mathbb{F}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_Y$ and every bijection $\varphi : M \rightarrow M'$ there exists a unique isomorphism $\Phi : X \rightarrow Y$ such that $\Phi|_M = \varphi$ and $\ddot{\Phi} = \bar{I}$.*

Corollary 13.12 ([1, 24.5.7]). *Let X be a Pappian projective space of finite rank. Every bijection $\varphi : M \rightarrow M'$ between two projective frames $M, M' \subseteq X$ extends to a unique projective automorphism of X .*

14. PROJECTIVE SPACES OF MODULES OVER CORPS

In this section we define and study an important example of a Desarguesian projective liner of algebraic origin.

Let X be an R -module over a corps R and $\mathbf{0}$ be the neutral element of the additive group of the R -module X . An *R -line* in the R -module X is any R -submodule $L \subseteq X$ of form $R \cdot x$ for some nonzero element $x \in X$.

The *projective space* $\mathbb{P}X$ of the R -module X is the set of R -lines $\{R \cdot b : b \in X \setminus \{\mathbf{0}\}\}$ endowed with the *canonical line structure* \mathcal{L} consisting of the lines

$$\overline{AC} := \{B \in \mathbb{P}X : B \subseteq A + B\},$$

where A, C are two distinct elements of the projective space $\mathbb{P}X$ and $A + C := \{a + c : a \in A, c \in C\}$.

From now on, we consider projective spaces over R -modules as liners endowed with their canonical line relations.

Proposition 14.1 ([1, 18.3.2+18.3.4]). *The projective space $\mathbb{P}X$ of any R -module X over a corps R is a 3-long projective liner with $|\mathbb{P}X|_2 = |R| + 1$.*

Proposition 14.2 ([1, 18.3.5]). *Let Y be an R -module over a corps R . For every R -submodule $X \subseteq Y$, the projective space $\mathbb{P}X$ is a flat subliner of the liner $\mathbb{P}Y$. If $X \neq Y$, then the projective liner $\mathbb{P}Y$ is a projective completion of the liner $\mathbb{P}Y \setminus \mathbb{P}X$.*

Lemma 14.3 ([1, 18.3.6]). *Let X be an R -module over a corps R and $\mathbb{P}X$ be its projective space. A subset $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathbb{P}X$ is flat in the liner $\mathbb{P}X$ if and only if $\bigcup \mathcal{A}$ is an R -submodule of the R -module X .*

Now we investigate the relation between the R -independence and independence in R -modules and their projective spaces.

Definition 14.4. Let X be an R -module over a corps R . A subset $B \subseteq X$ is called *R -independent* in the R -module X if every finitely supported function $f : B \rightarrow R$ with $\mathbf{0} = \sum_{b \in B} f(b) \cdot b$ has empty support $\text{supp}(f)$ and hence is the zero function.

Lemma 14.5 ([1, 18.3.8]). *A subset B of an R -module X over a corps R is R -independent if and only if $\mathbf{0} \notin B$, $R \cdot a \neq R \cdot b$ for any distinct elements $a, b \in B$, and the set $\mathbb{P}B := \{R \cdot b : b \in B\}$ is independent in the liner $\mathbb{P}X$.*

Definition 14.6. A set B in an R -module X over a corps X is called an *R -base* for X if for every element $x \in X$ there exists a unique finitely supported function $f \in R^{\oplus B}$ such that $x = \sum_{b \in B} f(b) \cdot b$.

Proposition 14.7 ([1, 18.3.10]). *For a set B in an R -module X over a corps R , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) B is an R -base for the R -module X ;
- (2) B is a maximal R -independent set in the R -module X ;
- (3) $\mathbf{0} \notin B$, $R \cdot a \neq R \cdot b$ for any distinct points $a, b \in B$, and the set $\{R \cdot b : b \in B\}$ is maximal independent in the liner $\mathbb{P}X$.

Corollary 14.8. *Let X be an R -module over a corps R . Every R -base B in the R -module X has cardinality $|B| = \|\mathbb{P}X\|$.*

Definition 14.9. For an R -module X over a corps R , its *R -dimension* $\dim_R(X)$ is defined as the cardinality of any R -base for X .

Corollary 14.8 ensures that any two R -bases in an R -module X over a corps R have the same cardinality, so the cardinal $\dim_R(X)$ is well-defined.

Definition 14.10. Let X be an R -module over a corps X . A subset $H \subseteq X$ is called an *R -hyperplane* in the R -module X if H is an R -submodule of X such that $H \neq X = H + R \cdot x$ for every $x \in X \setminus H$.

Lemma 14.11 ([1, 18.3.14]). *Let X be an R -module over a corps R . A subset $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathbb{P}X$ is a hyperplane in the liner $\mathbb{P}X$ if and only if $\bigcup \mathcal{H}$ is an R -hyperplane in the R -module X .*

Proposition 14.12 ([1, 18.3.15]). *Let X be an R -module over a corps $R \neq \{0, 1\}$ and H be an R -hyperplane in X . The liner H is isomorphic to the subliner $\mathbb{P}X \setminus \mathbb{P}H$ of the projective liner $\mathbb{P}X$, and hence $\mathbb{P}X$ is isomorphic to the spread completion of the affine regular liner H .*

Theorem 14.13 ([1, 18.3.16]). *The projective space $\mathbb{P}X$ of any R -module X over a corps R is a 3-long Desarguesian projective liner of rank $\|\mathbb{P}X\| = \dim_R(X)$ and $|\mathbb{P}X|_2 = 1 + |R|$.*

Theorem 14.14 ([1, 18.3.17]). *A projective space Y is Desarguesian if and only if it is isomorphic to the projective space $\mathbb{P}X$ of some R -module X over a corps R .*

15. AUTOMORPHISMS OF DESARGUESIAN PROJECTIVE SPACES

The following theorem establishes an important homogeneity properties of projective spaces of modules over corps.

Theorem 15.1 ([1, 18.4.1]). *Let X be an R -module over a corps R and $\mathcal{B}, \mathcal{B}'$ be two maximal independent sets in the projective space $\mathbb{P}X$. Every bijection $F : \mathcal{B} \rightarrow \mathcal{B}'$ extends to an automorphism $\bar{F} : \mathbb{P}X \rightarrow \mathbb{P}X$ of the liner $\mathbb{P}X$.*

Theorems 15.1 and 14.14 imply the following important fact.

Theorem 15.2 ([1, 18.4.2]). *Every bijection $\phi : M \rightarrow M'$ between maximal independent sets in a Desarguesian projective space X extends to an automorphism of the liner X .*

Corollary 15.3 ([1, 18.4.3]). *For every hyperplanes H, H' in a Desarguesian projective space X and every flat $\Pi \subseteq H \cap H'$, there exists an automorphism $\Phi : X \rightarrow X$ such that $\Phi[\Pi] = \Pi$, $\Phi[H] = H'$.*

Corollary 15.4 ([1, 18.4.4]). *For any hyperplanes H, H' in a Desarguesian projective space X , the affine liners $X \setminus H$ and $X \setminus H'$ are isomorphic.*

Corollary 15.5 ([1, 18.4.5]). *Two Desarguesian affine spaces X, Y are isomorphic if and only if their spread completions are isomorphic.*

In fact, Corollary 15.5 can be generalized to Thalesian affine spaces.

Theorem 15.6 ([1, 18.4.6]). *Two Thalesian affine spaces are isomorphic if and only if their spread completions are isomorphic.*

Theorem 15.6 allows us to define the *scalar corps* \mathbb{R}_X of every projective space X as follows. If for some hyperplane $H \subseteq X$, the affine liner $A := X \setminus H$ is a Thalesian affine space, then put $\mathbb{R}_X := \mathbb{R}_A$. Theorem 15.6 ensures that the isomorphic type of the corps \mathbb{R}_A does not depend on the choice of the hyperplane $H \subseteq X$ with Thalesian complement. If for every hyperplane $H \subseteq X$ the complement $X \setminus H$ is not a Thalesian affine space, then put $\mathbb{R}_X := \{0, 1\}$ be the two-element field. In particular, $\mathbb{R}_X = \{0, 1\}$ for any Steiner projective liner X .

Proposition 15.7 ([1, 18.4.7]). *Let X be an R -module over a corps R . If $\dim_R(X) \geq 3$, then the scalar corps $\mathbb{R}_{\mathbb{P}X}$ of the projective space $\mathbb{P}X$ is isomorphic to the corps R .*

16. ISOMORPHIC CLASSIFICATION OF DESARGUESIAN PROAFFINE SPACES

Theorem 16.1 ([1, 18.5.1]). *Every Desarguesian projective space X is isomorphic to the projective space $\mathbb{P}\mathbb{R}_X^{\oplus \|X\|}$ of the \mathbb{R}_X -module $\mathbb{R}_X^{\oplus \|X\|}$.*

Corollary 16.2 ([1, 18.5.2]). *Two Desarguesian projective spaces X, Y are isomorphic if and only if $\|X\| = \|Y\|$ and the corps \mathbb{R}_X and \mathbb{R}_Y are isomorphic.*

Theorem 16.3 ([1, 18.5.3]). *Two Desarguesian proaffine spaces X, Y are isomorphic if and only if $\|\partial X\| = \|\partial Y\|$, $\|\bar{X}\|_{\partial X} = \|\bar{Y}\|_{\partial Y}$ and the corps \mathbb{R}_X and \mathbb{R}_Y are isomorphic.*

Theorem 16.3 motivates the problem of classifying corps up to an isomorphism. For finite corps the answer is known and classical: *two finite corps are isomorphic if and only if they have the same cardinality*, see Wedderburn–Dickson–Witt Theorems 18.6.1 and Moore Theorem 18.6.6 in [1].

Theorem 16.4 ([1, 18.7.3]). *Two 3-long finite Desarguesian proaffine regular liners X, Y are isomorphic if and only if $|X| = |Y|$ and $\|X\| = \|Y\|$.*

Theorem 16.4 follows from Theorem 16.3, the classification of finite corps and the following proposition calculating the cardinality of a finite completely regular liner.

Proposition 16.5. *Every 3-long finite completely regular liner X has cardinality*

$$|X| = \frac{(|\bar{X}|_2 - 1)^{\|X\|} - (|\bar{X}|_2 - 1)^{\|\partial X\|}}{|\bar{X}|_2 - 2}.$$

17. THE AUTOMORPHISM GROUPS OF PAPPIAN PROJECTIVE SPACES

Theorem 17.1 ([1, 24.6.1]). *Let X be a Pappian projective space, r be a projective reper in X , and $\text{Aut}_r(X) := \{A \in \text{Aut}(X) : \forall x \in \text{dom}[r] \cup \text{rng}[r] \ A(x) = x\}$. Then $\text{Aut}_r(X)$ is a subgroup of the group $\text{Aut}(X)$ such that $\text{Aut}_r(X) \cap \text{Proj}(X) = \{1_X\}$, $\text{Aut}(X) = \text{Proj}(X) \cdot \text{Aut}_r(X)$ and the function $\text{Aut}_r(X) \rightarrow \text{Aut}(\mathbb{F}_X)$, $A \mapsto \bar{A}$, is a group isomorphism.*

Theorem 17.1 implies the following description of the automorphism group of a Pappian projective space.

Corollary 17.2 ([1, 24.6.2]). *The automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$ of a Pappian projective space X is a semidirect product $\text{Proj}(X) \rtimes \text{Aut}(\mathbb{F}_X)$ of the groups $\text{Proj}(X)$ and $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{F}_X)$.*

Remark 17.3 ([1, 24.6.3]). By Theorem 14.14, every Desarguesian projective space X of finite rank $\|X\| = n$ is isomorphic to the projective space $\mathbb{P}\mathbb{R}_X^n$. For a field F , the group of projective automorphisms of the projective space $\mathbb{P}F^n$ is isomorphic to the *projective linear group* $PGL(n, F) := GL(n, F)/\mathcal{Z}(GL(n, F))$, where $GL(n, F)$ is the group of invertible $n \times n$ -matrices with coefficients in the field F , and $\mathcal{Z}(GL(n, F)) = \{c \cdot I : c \in F\}$ is the center of the group $GL(n, F)$. If the field F is finite, then the group $PGL(n, F)$ is denoted by $PGL(n, q)$ where $q = |F|$ (because fields of the same cardinality are isomorphic). In 1870 Camille Jordan proved that for every finite field F of cardinality $|F| \notin \{2, 3\}$ and every number $n \geq 2$, the projective linear group $PGL(n, F)$ is simple (= has only two normal subgroups).

Applying Corollary 17.2, we can calculate the cardinality of the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$ of a finite Pappian projective space X and its normal subgroup $\text{Proj}(X)$, consisting of projective automorphisms.

Theorem 17.4 ([1, 24.7.1]). *For every finite Pappian projective space X , the group $\text{Proj}(X)$ of projective automorphisms of X has cardinality*

$$|\text{Proj}(X)| = \frac{1}{\ell - 1} \prod_{k=0}^{\|X\|-1} (\ell^{\|X\|} - \ell^k),$$

where $\ell := |\mathbb{F}_X| = |X|_2 - 1$.

Theorem 17.5 ([1, 24.7.2]). *For every finite Pappian projective space X , the automorphism group of X has cardinality*

$$|\text{Aut}(X)| = |\text{Aut}(\mathbb{F}_X)| \cdot |\text{Proj}(X)| = \frac{n}{\ell - 1} \cdot \prod_{k=0}^{\|X\|-1} (\ell^{\|X\|} - \ell^k),$$

where $r := \|X\|$ and $\ell := |X|_2 - 1$.

18. HOMOGENEITY OF DESARGUESIAN PROAFFINE SPACES

We recall that a liner X is called a *space* if X is 3-long, regular and has rank $\|X\| \geq 3$.

Theorem 18.1 ([1, 18.9.1]). *For any points x, y of a Desarguesian proaffine space X , there exists an automorphism $F : X \rightarrow X$ such that $F(x) = y$.*

Definition 18.2. A liner X is called

- *point-homogeneous* if for every points $x, y \in X$ there exists an automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ such that $A(x) = y$;
- *line-homogeneous* if for every lines L, Λ in X there exists an automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ such that $A[L] = \Lambda$.

Theorem 18.1 implies that Desarguesian proaffine spaces are point-homogeneous.

Corollary 18.3 ([1, 18.9.3]). *Every Desarguesian proaffine space is point-homogeneous.*

Example 18.4. A finite punctured projective plane is not line-homogeneous because it contains lines of different cardinalities.

Nonetheless, we have the following weaker line-homogeneity property of Desarguesian proaffine spaces.

Proposition 18.5 ([1, 18.9.5]). *Let L, Λ be two lines in a Desarguesian proaffine space X . If the lines L, Λ are both spreading or both non-spreading, then for every distinct points $o, e \in L$ and any distinct points $o', e' \in \Lambda$, there exists an automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ such that $Aoe = o'e'$ and hence $A[L] = \Lambda$.*

Corollary 18.6 ([1, 18.9.6]). *A Desarguesian proaffine space X is line-homogeneous if and only if X is affine or projective.*

19. AUTOMORPHISMS OF FINITE DESARGUESIAN PROAFFINE SPACES

By Corollary 18.3, every Desarguesian proaffine space is point-homogeneous. In this section we calculate the cardinality of the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$ of a finite Desarguesian proaffine space.

By [1, 10.6.15], every Desarguesian proaffine space is completely regular, and by [1, 10.9.1], its spread completion \bar{X} is a Desarguesian projective space. By [1, 8.2.11], every automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a X uniquely extends to an automorphism $\bar{A} : \bar{X} \rightarrow \bar{X}$ of the spread completion \bar{X} of X . So, the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$ of X can be identified with the subgroup

$$\text{Aut}(\bar{X}, \partial X) := \{\bar{A} \in \text{Aut}(\bar{X}) : \bar{A}[\partial X] = \partial X\}.$$

This observation allows to calculate the cardinality of the automorphism group of any finite Desarguesian proaffine space.

Theorem 19.1 ([1, 24.8.1]). *The automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$ of a finite Desarguesian proaffine space X has cardinality*

$$|\text{Aut}(X)| = \frac{n}{\ell - 1} \cdot \prod_{k=0}^{\|\partial X\| - 1} (\ell^{\|\partial X\| - k} - \ell^k) \cdot \prod_{k=\|\partial X\|}^{\|X\| - 1} (\ell^{\|X\| - k} - \ell^k),$$

where $\ell = |\bar{X}|_2 - 1$ is the order of the projective completion \bar{X} of X .

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